

A convenient procedure for bis-esterification of cyclic anhydrides

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Abstract : Aromatic and aliphatic cyclic anhydrides are chemoselectively and conveniently transformed to the corresponding diesters by the use of DBU and appropriate alkyl/allyl halides. This bis-esterification reaction has been exemplified mostly with dimethyl esters. But in some cases, mixed dialkyl esters are also prepared.

Keywords : Anhydrides, DBU, bis-esterification, chemoselective, mixed dialkyl diesters.

Introduction

Esterification is a fundamentally important process in organic chemistry. There is a plethora of reported procedures in the chemical literature and newer methods are continually being developed^{1,2}. Recently, we reported the facility with which DBU-CH₃I promotes chemoselective esterification of carboxylic acids^{3,4}. The conventional literature methods involve refluxing cyclic anhydrides with methanol in presence of an acid catalyst (e.g. HCl⁵, H₂SO₄⁶, PTSA⁷, SOCl₂⁸, etc.). Alternatively, methanolysis of anhydrides followed by treatment with CH₂N₂² or TMSCHN₂⁹ is adopted for the preparation of dimethyl esters from cyclic anhydrides. We propose that the reaction of an anhydride (**1**) with methanol would form a half ester (**2**), which, in turn, would react with an alkyl halide (Scheme 1) to give diester (**3**) in one operation. This would thus constitute a method, complementary to the commonly used methods¹⁰.

Scheme 1. Proposed steps for bis-esterification of cyclic anhydrides.

Results and discussion

We began this work with examination of two simple anhydrides, namely succinic anhydride (**1a**) and glutaric

anhydride (**1b**). In both the cases, treatment of these anhydrides (**1a** and **1b**) with methanol at room temperature in the presence of DBU (1 equiv) followed by iodomethane (2 equiv) resulted in facile formation of the corresponding diesters **3a**¹¹ and **3b**^{12,13} (entries 1 and 2) respectively in good yields. The method was then tested with several more complex anhydrides. The results are summarized in Table 1. The reaction between the anhydride **1e** with DBU in methanol followed by CH₃I furnished the dimethyl ester **3e**¹⁴ in 77% yield under unoptimized conditions. Conventionally, ketal-containing anhydrides are normally converted to the dimethyl esters in two stages : (i) methanolysis with methanol and (ii) *O*-methylation of the resulting half esters with TMSCHN₂ or Me₂SO₄, K₂CO₃ in DMF^{5,9,15}.

With a view to developing an operationally simpler method for mixed dialkyl esters, we investigated the reactivity of a series of maleic anhydrides (entries 7-10). Maleic anhydride **1g** was first submitted to the reaction with CH₃OH-DBU-CH₃I at room temperature and the desired dimethyl ester **3g**¹⁶ was obtained in 71% yield. The isomeric *trans* diester was not formed¹⁷. Under identical conditions, methyl maleic anhydride **1h** afforded *cis* diester **3h**¹⁸ in 92% yield. In order to test the feasibility of preparing mixed dialkyl ester, maleic anhydride (**1g**) was submitted to methanolysis with MeOH in the presence of DBU followed by *in situ* alkylation with allyl bromide. Work-up of the reaction mixture afforded the

desired mixed diester (**3i**) in 44% yield. Treatment of maleic anhydride (**1g**) with DBU in *tert*-butanol followed by CH_3I furnished diester **3j**¹⁹ in 43% yield. This preparation of *tert*-butyl methyl maleate (**3j**) involving *tert*-butanol-DBU-iodomethane is more convenient than the literature method involving the reaction of maleic anhydride (**1g**) with anhydrous methanol in the presence of sodium methoxide followed by *tert*-butylation with isobutylene in methylene chloride in the presence of sulfuric acid¹⁷.

It is noteworthy that the conversion of the diacid **1k** to diester **3n** with methanol in the presence of Dowex 50W is a low-yielding (~40%) and time consuming process. Esterification of **1m** with 2.5 equiv of MeI gave a complex mixture of dimethyl ester **3p**²⁰ and trimethyl ester

3q²¹. The value of the present method is best illustrated by diesterification of the unstable anhydride **1n**, which is susceptible to aromatization to **3s** under conventional conditions⁵⁻⁹. Diesterification of **1n** with MeOH-DBU-MeI system at room temperature worked out well to give dimethyl ester **3r** in 75% yield. The product was characterized by analysis of ¹H NMR spectrum. A small amount (<5%) of aromatic diester **3s** was also obtained. Rapid decomposition of **3r** to **3s** occurred upon standing.

In summary, the transformation of cyclic anhydrides to diesters, generalized with a number of examples, is accomplished in one pot at room temperature in good yields. It is also applicable for preparation of mixed dialkyl diesters, specifically *tert*-butyl methyl ester (entry 10) without resorting to isobutylene gas¹⁴.

Table 1. Conversion of cyclic anhydrides to diesters with ROH-DBU-R'X

Entry No.	Anhydrides	Diesters	Yield (%)	¹ H NMR	¹³ C NMR
1	 1a	3a^{a,b}	80		
2	 1b	3b^{a,b}	65	(200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.61 (6H, s), 2.32 (4H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.87 (2H, quin, J 7.2 Hz)	(50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 173.4, 51.6, 33.0, 20.0
3	 1c	3c^{a,b}	74	(400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.66 (2H, s), 3.68 (6H, s), 3.04 (2H, t, J 4.8 Hz), 2.55 (2H, dd, J 4.8 Hz, 16 Hz), 2.35 (2H, dd, J 5.6 Hz, 16.8 Hz)	(100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 173.7, 125.0, 51.7, 39.6, 25.6
4	 1d	3d^{a,c}	70	(200 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.19 (2H, t), 3.55 (6H, s), 3.24 (2H, m), 3.10 (2H, m), 1.44 (1H, dt, J 1.8 Hz, 5.0 Hz), 1.28 (1H, d, J 8.6 Hz)	(50 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 172.8, 134.8, 51.4, 48.6, 48.4, 46.2
5	 1e	3e^{a,g}	77	(400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.82 (2H, s), 3.67 (6H, s), 3.62 (3H, s), 3.56 (3H, s)	(100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 168.2, 129.6, 112.7, 54.8, 53.1, 52.4, 52.0
6	 1f	3f^{a,b}	62	(400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.02 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.49 (1H, t, J 7.4 Hz), 7.37 (1H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 7.27-7.26 (1H, m), 4.01 (2H, s), 3.87 (3H, s), 3.70 (3H, s)	(100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 171.9, 167.4, 135.9, 132.4, 132.2, 131.0, 129.5, 127.4, 52.0, 51.9, 40.5

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

7		3g^{a,b}	71	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 6.87 (2H), 3.81 (6H, s)	
8		3h^{a,b}	92	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 5.84 (1H, q, <i>J</i> 1.5 Hz), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.70 (3H, s), 2.04 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 1.5 Hz)	(50 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 169.3, 165.3, 145.6, 120.5, 52.3, 51.7, 20.4
9		3i^{d,b}	44	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 6.27 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 4 Hz), 5.90–5.98 (1H, m), 5.36 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 16 Hz, 1.2 Hz), 5.27 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 10.4 Hz), 4.69 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 4.8 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s)	(50 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 165.7, 164.8, 131.6, 130.0, 129.6, 119.0, 65.9, 52.2
10		3j^{e,b}	43	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 6.19 (1H, ABd, <i>J</i> 12 Hz), 6.11 (1H, ABd, <i>J</i> 12 Hz), 3.78 (3H, s), 1.50 (9H, s)	(50 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 165.7, 164.3, 131.8, 127.6, 82.1, 51.8, 27.9
11		3k^{a,b}	90	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 7.75–7.69 (2H, m), 7.57–7.51 (2H, m), 3.91 (6H, s)	
12		3l^{f,b}	65	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 7.73–7.76 (2H, m), 7.52–7.56 (2H, m), 5.94–6.05 (2H, m), 5.38 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 17.2 Hz), 5.28 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 10.4 Hz), 4.79 (4H, d, <i>J</i> 5.6 Hz)	(100 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 167.2, 132, 131.8, 131.1, 129, 118.6, 66.3
13		3m^{a,b}	55	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 7.80 (2H, s), 3.90 (6H, s)	(50 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 166.0, 135.8, 131.4, 130.9, 53.1
14		3n^{a,b}	65	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 9.07 (1H, s), 8.83 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz), 7.50 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5 Hz), 3.95 (6H, s)	
15		3o^{a,g}	89	(400 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 8.00 (4H, m), 7.55 (2H, m), 3.91 (6H, s)	(100 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 169.2, 134.1, 132.4, 130.1, 129.6, 127.3, 125.2, 52.0
16		3p^{a,g}	30	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 8.24 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 3.4 Hz), 8.17 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, 1.6 Hz), 7.80 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz), 3.83 (6H, s)	(100 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 167.5, 166.6, 166.1, 136.0, 133.7, 132.9, 131.2, 129.9, 129.5, 53.3

Table-1 (contd.)

17	 1n	3q ^{a,b}	40	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 8.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 1.6 Hz), 8.18 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 1.8 Hz, 8.2 Hz), 7.73 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz), 3.93 (3H, s), 3.91 (6H, s)	(50 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 167.6, 166.8, 165.4, 136.2, 132.5, 132.3, 131.6, 130.3, 128.9, 52.9, 52.8, 52.6
		3r ^{h,b}	75	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 5.57 (1H, br s), 5.43 (1H, br s), 3.71 (3H, s), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.10– 3.25 (2H, m), 2.3–2.5 (2H, m), 2.03 (3H, s), 1.95–1.25 (7H, m)	
		3s ^{h,b}	<5	(200 MHz, CDCl ₃) : δ 7.73 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz), 7.16 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz), 3.94 (3H, s), 3.87 (3H, s), 2.82 (2H, m), 2.72 (2H, m), 1.79 (4H, quin, <i>J</i> 3 Hz)	

^aMeOH, DBU, MeI (5 equiv); ^bcolorless oil; ^csemisolid; ^dMeOH, DBU, allyl bromide; ^etBuOH, DBU, MeI; ^fallyl alcohol, DBU, allyl bromide; ^gsolid; ^hMeOH, DBU, MeI (9 equiv).

Experimental

Melting points are determined on a Sunbim melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Thermo Nicolet Nexus 870 FT-IR spectrophotometers using KBr pellet. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of the samples in the indicated solvents were recorded on 200 MHz and 400 MHz spectrometer (Brücker) in CDCl₃ with TMS as the internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ unit and coupling constant in Hz. Dry solvents used for reactions were purified, before use, according to the standard protocols²². All solvents for chromatography were distilled prior to use. Columns were prepared with silica gel (60–120 or 230–400 mesh). The phrase “usual work-up” or ‘worked up in usual manner’ refers to washing of the organic phase with water (2 × 1/4 the volume of organic phase) and brine (1 × 1/4 the volume of organic phase), and drying (Na₂SO₄), filtration, and concentration under reduced pressure.

Typical experimental procedure for bis-esterification of cyclic anhydrides :

DBU (2 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of an anhydride (1 mmol) in dry methanol (or the respective alcohol) (5 mL) at room temperature and the reaction mixture was stirred for 10 min. Iodomethane or the alkyl halide (5 mmol) was added to the mixture over a period

of 5–10 min, and stirring was continued for 3–4 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and diluted with ethyl acetate (50 mL). The resulting solution was washed successively with water (10 mL), saturated aqueous solution of sodium thiosulfate (5 mL) and brine (10 mL). The organic layer was dried and concentrated. The residue was purified by silica-gel filtration or preparative thin-layer chromatography to afford pure diesters. In most cases, treatment of the organic layer with brine during work-up leads to a NMR-pure product.

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References

1. J. Otera, "Esterification : Methods, Reactions and Applications", Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co, Weinheim, 2003, pp. 1-326.
2. E. Kuhnle, D. D. P. Laffan, G. C. Lloyd-Jones, T. Martinez del Campo, I. R. Shepperson and J. L. Slaughter, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, 46, 7075.
3. D. Mal, A. Jana, S. Ray, S. Bhattacharya, A. Patra and S.

Note

- R. De, *Synth. Commun.*, 2008, **38**, 3937.
- D. Mal, *Synth. Commun.*, 1986, **16**, 331.
 - J. S. Yadav and P. K. Sasmal, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 5185.
 - A. Kar and N. P. Argade, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 7131.
 - H. Uno, H. Watanabe, Y. Yamashita and N. Ono, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2005, **3**, 448.
 - G. Deguest, L. Bischoff, C. Fruit and F. Marsais, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **17**, 2120.
 - K. Miyamoto, Y. Sei, K. Yamaguchi and M. Ochiai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 1382.
 - F. Luo, C. Pan, P. Qian and J. Cheng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **75**, 5379.
 - Z. Meng and S. J. Danishefsky, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 1511.
 - C. Gaviglio and F. Doctorovich, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 5379.
 - K. Miyamoto, Y. Sei, K. Yamaguchi and M. Ochiai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 1382.
 - F. A. Khan and B. Prabhudas, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 9289.
 - J. Alexander, G. Lowe, N. K. McCullum and G. K. Ruffles, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 2092.
 - B. Erb, J-P. Kucma, S. Mourey and F. Struber, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2003, **9**, 2582.
 - A. G. Cook, A. B. Voges and A. E. Kammrath, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7349.
 - B. Brazdova, N. S. Tan, N. M. Samoshina and V. V. Samoshin, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 2009, **344**, 311.
 - S. F. Nelsen and J. P. Gillespie, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 2391.
 - S. Kasina and J. Nematollahi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, **19**, 1403.
 - A. M. Castano, A. M. Echavarren, J. Lopez and A. Santos, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1989, **379**, 171.
 - D. Mal, M. Bandhyopadhyay, K. Datta and K. V. S. N. Murty, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **54**, 7525.

